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Microcredentials and the Future of learning

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ARE MICROCREDENTIALS BECOMING A BIG DEAL?

MICROCREDENTIALS

2020-2023
Cedefop study on VET and LM

2021
Cedefop supports EC and the SWD with data from VET

2022
EC Council Recommendation MCs for LLL and employability

2023 - 2025
EU MS are increasingly embedding MCs in their ET systems

2025 - 2027
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New research: Deepening on MCs

Four scenarios for microcredentials

Scenario 1: Supply-driven microcredentials (as part of formal education) for further learning

Scenario 2: Supply-driven microcredentials for LM entry and job setting (professional credentials)

Scenario 3: Demand-driven microcredentials (examples of enterprises/sectors)

Scenario 4: Microcredentials for vulnerable groups /groups at risk (upskilling/reskilling)

Source: [Pouliou, A. \(2024\)](#)

What is the position of MCs (in focus) in the wider landscape of non-formal ET?

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Methodology

Literature study / scoping interviews in Spring 2025

EU-wide survey on MC:

- ✓ Collecting descriptions of microcredential(-like) offers outside formal domain
- ✓ Complemented by national experts
- ✓ Targeted follow-up calls

WA1: Exploring the diversity of MCs

8 Case studies

- Desk research
- Expert interviews
- Pilot-phase concluded in **BE, AT**
- Next stage: HR, DK, EE, EL, IT, SK

WA2: Focus on LM sectors

Sectoral case studies on Construction & Cultural / Creative Industries

- Desk research
- Expert interviews

WA3: MC role for social inclusion

Overview all EU countries

- Desk research
- Cedefop ReferNet questionnaire (27 EU Member States)

Typology of MCs

(1) **Non-formal MC by providers of formal programmes:** Benefit from the institutional quality assurance systems already in place within their issuing organisations

(2) **Professional competence certificates:** Certificates showcase the practical skills and knowledge required for specific occupations. Professional competence certificates are subject to some level of public oversight

(3) **International standard based credentials:** Not linked to broader qualification systems, developed or endorsed by professional associations, industry bodies or specialist training providers. QA is varied, depending on international standard

(4) **Sector-recognised credentials:** Certify workers for the requirements set out by professional groups. Learning content, certification and quality assurance are developed by the sector itself

(5) **Employer-issued credentials:** Awarded for programmes offered by (providers contracted by) companies directly, with demands on QA typically governed by the employer itself

(6) **Badges:** Most flexible form which allows to validate acquired skill or knowledge, with non-standard and decentralised approach to QA

What are the operational characteristics of MCs (in focus)?

1. Credential Identification and Issuance:

- Title of the microcredential.
- Issuing body (type of provider)
- Country/region of the issuer.
- Issuance of a digital credential (creation of a digital portfolio)

2. Learning Outcomes and qualifications level:

- Defined learning outcomes (knowledge, skills, autonomy, and responsibility).
- Level of the qualification (e.g. level in national system/framework, equivalent NQF/EQF level (NB: indicate whether the MC formally has this NQF/EQF level, or whether the MC could informally be positioned at a certain NQF/EQF level)).
- Relationship to occupational fields, labour market sector, or tasks.

3. Workload and Credits:

- Notional workload required to achieve learning outcomes (e.g., ECTS, hours of learning).

4. Assessment and Certification:

- Type of assessment used (e.g., written, practice-oriented, mixed).
- Basis for awarding the credential (e.g., participation in programme, validation of prior learning, assessment only).
- Use of external assessment

5. Pedagogical and Delivery Features:

- Delivery format (e.g., online, face-to-face, blended).
- Learning site (e.g., workplace, classroom, dual learning environments).
- Role of the teacher (e.g., facilitator, lecturer).
- Control over learning (e.g., self-directed or teacher-centred).

6. Access:

- Entry requirements for the credential.

7. Use of the MC in formal education and outside

- Accumulation or stackability of MCs (possibility of combining MCs towards a qualification)
- Potential for automatic recognition across borders or institutions (NB: ability to integrate the MC (acquired elsewhere) in a formal VET/HE qualification).

8. Stakeholder Relevance:

- Engagement with industry or employers in designing the credential.
- Relevance of the credential to labour market needs.
- Transparency and clarity for learners, employers, and education providers.

Operational characteristics of MCs: interim findings

6 KEY FEATURES OF MICROCREDENTIALS AWARDED OUTSIDE FORMAL EDUCATION

VARIETY OF TRAINING PROVIDERS

VARIETY OF LEARNING CONTEXT

DIVERSITY OF LEARNING FORMATS

RELATIVELY HIGH USE OF LEARNING OUTCOMES

USE OF DIGITALLY VERIFIABLE CREDENTIALS

MICROCREDENTIALS ARE MAINLY STAND-ALONE OR SECTOR-SPECIFIC

Source: Cedefop (forthcoming), 'Image of 6 key features of microcredentials awarded outside formal education' prompt. ChatGPT, 21 October 2025

Training providers offering MCs outside the formal domain

Providers offering programmes in the formal domain e.g. universities and VET institutions

Private training providers

Sectoral organisations

Employers: companies designing and issuing training certificates

NGOs and community initiatives

Example of a MC offered by an employer (scenario 3)

Example from case study: AT - “Platform winter service”

The Austrian national railway operator ÖBB offers **modular training courses** on **rail safety**. The courses can be attended by employees, in the context of their professional training, as well as outsiders. Although the courses are aimed at those working in the railway industry, admission is open to anyone who speaks sufficient German.

One of these modules is ‘Platform winter service’ (Bahnsteig Winterdienst): a course that trains participants to work on railway platforms in a safe manner during winter conditions. The courses consist of 10 training sessions and conclude with a certificate of attendance, or an exam upon request. The value of this credential lies in the **value attributed to the provider** and its experience in working in wintery conditions, there is no formal recognition of the course or the credential, nor is there an EQF-level attached to the credential.

Source: Cedefop (forthcoming)

Use of digitally verified credentials

Source: Cedefop (forthcoming)

Higher education institutions and VET centres are mostly issuing digital credentials, offering transcripts, digital certificates, or badges.

Credentials issued by sectoral bodies and employers are mostly paper-based or distributed in the form of a pdf, which limits external verifiability.

The Main Functions of Microcredentials Across Stakeholders

For learners and employees

The most common function identified is to support **upskilling (51%)** and **reskilling (22%)**, while only about 7.5% target basic competences or disadvantaged groups

Microcredentials tend to be mainly used in sectors that labour market transitions are most pressing across Europe

For employers and sector bodies

The function of MCs can best be summarised as a way to respond to specific occupational or compliance needs, and allow the strengthening sectoral coordination and professional standards

Companies may consider sector-recognised credentials and international standard-based certificates as conditions for employment or progression

For training providers

They represent tools for innovation and responsiveness (to labour market needs), and in specific contexts can be used to bridge formal and non-formal learning offers

Microcredentials with a LM orientation are not defined by a single logic, but by the **interplay** between stakeholders.

Source: Cedefop (forthcoming). 'Image of the main functions of MCs across stakeholders' prompt. ChatGPT, 21 October 2025

Quality assurance and recognition

- Which are the elements to consider a microcredential as **'quality assured'**?
- How can **cooperation, governance and partnership** be ensured so that different stakeholders **co-develop, co-design and update** microcredentials?
- How can QA agencies adapt quality assurance **mechanisms** for microcredentials issued by **different types of providers**?
- Are microcredentials tools to **recognise prior learning and competences** or tools to increase **accessibility** in education and employment?

Recognition of labour market-oriented MCs

- MCs outside the formal domain of education tend **to have few links** to NQFs or to formal programmes
- MCs awarded through **internal** company training are **less likely to be transferable**
- MCs usually recognised within a sector, with very **limited portability** across sectors or borders
- Training providers pointed to **administrative and regulatory burdens**
- Need to balance **flexibility** with **credibility**

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Which are the main elements to consider a microcredential 'quality assured'?

Accredited
QA systems

Credentials
offered by setoral
organisations

degree of
public
involvement

Source: Cedefop (forthcoming), 'Image of main elements to consider a microcredential 'quality assured'' prompt. ChatGPT, 21 October 2025

- ❖ **In Flanders**, government-coordinated QA, which explicitly focuses on incorporating labour-market input has the potential to strengthen the quality approach.
- ❖ **In Austria**, a looser structure of decentralised QA yields autonomy to individual providers, but reduces comparability between credentials within and beyond sectors

What are the QA procedures underpinning MCs?

❖ **Key features** of underpinning QA systems

- ❖ Type of quality assurance mechanism (certification, quality awards, inspection, self-assessment)
- ❖ Responsible body for QA (government agency, department, ngo, other)
- ❖ Scope of assessment (organisation level, or programme level)
- ❖ Costs (what costs are involved)

❖ **Assessment process**

- ❖ Quality-assessed training elements (External quality certificate, leadership and management, ongoing monitoring, organisational structure, public information, quality management system, regulatory compliance, staff recruitment and training, training design and delivery)
- ❖ Assessment tools and methods (Analysis of performance indicators, expert reviews, interviews, self-assessment questionnaires, site visits, surveys)

❖ **Assessment outcomes**

- ❖ Grading system (fail/pass, or multi-category grading systems)
- ❖ Validity period of the outcome (in years)
- ❖ Benefits to providers (Display of quality label, eligibility for public funding, licence to operate, listing in a registry of providers, award)

❖ **Additional features:**

- ❖ QA informed by relevant regional and international standards and guidelines
- ❖ Regulations related to ensuring the involvement of labour market stakeholders in:
 - ❖ Designing, developing and implementing microcredentials;
 - ❖ The QA process (and the role these stakeholders have).

MCs and labour market sector relevance

- How can **sector-specific** microcredentials provide targeted learning achievements and learning opportunities?
- Do microcredentials focus on **occupation/job specific learning outcomes, on transversal skills and competences** or on both of them?
- To what extent are such microcredentials used by employers in **recruitment procedures** in comparison to full qualifications?

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Current research:

- Construction sector (green focus)
- Cultural and creative industries (CCI)

Reasons for selecting CCI

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- ❖ It combines **artistic and cultural** creativity with commercial and economic activity.
- ❖ It encompasses a **wide range of subsectors and occupations** (like performing arts, visual arts, design, advertising, publishing, and film) all of which produce goods and services with cultural and symbolic value.
- ❖ CCIs are **considered important drivers of economic growth**, innovation, and social development
- ❖ **8.7 million** people employed
- ❖ Embedded in **traditional** skills but a shift due to AI and digital skills
- ❖ Diversity of sector means **insights applied to a range of other economic sectors**

Zooming in on construction sector (focus on greening)

- ❖ **Widespread** with large and small employers, a large share of migrant workers and institutionalised social dialogue
- ❖ **A total of 5.6 million persons**, or 3% of the total workforce, are employed in either construction of buildings or civil engineering in the EU
- ❖ **Green transition:** huge impact on the sector- EU Renovation Wave Strategy and Energy Performance of Buildings Directive pushing fwd change with in-demand skills
- ❖ Sector undergoing **digital transformation**, new digital tools for management and planning requiring advanced skills
- ❖ Microcredentials are **directly included in sectoral strategies:** Engineers for Europe Skills Strategy
- ❖ Sector provides opportunity to **focus on TSCs** (interpersonal skills)

The evolving role of MCs for social inclusion

- Are microcredentials exchanged and accumulated to **facilitate lifelong and life-wide learning** of **disadvantaged** individuals?
- Which **supporting measures** can be taken for disadvantaged end users?
- Which **recommendations and implementation guidelines** on microcredentials can be developed to support disadvantaged end users?

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Overall reflections

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Overall reflections

MC **ecosystems** can only be understood in relation to their governance configurations:

- ❖ the degree of state involvement,
 - ❖ the strength of sectoral coordination,
 - ❖ and the way validation systems are structured.
- ❑ The examples collected through the survey and case studies shows the **diversity of credentials with a labour-market orientation**
 - ❑ The mix of providers of microcredentials with a labour market orientation is **broad but uneven**
 - ❑ **Recognition** remains **fragmented**

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The **future** of Microcredentials

- ❖ Microcredentials as a learning revolution
- ❖ Empowering learners, workers & employers
- ❖ Essential for future-ready skills

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Microcredentials in Europe Publications

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BRIEFING NOTE

MICROCREDENTIALS

STRIVING TO COMBINE CREDIBILITY AND AGILITY

Sweeping changes in economies and jobs require education and training to offer more flexible learning pathways and valid credentials

Microcredentials hold promise for connecting people's skillsets with labour market demand in a rapidly changing world of work. They have proliferated in recent years across economic sectors and education levels, reinforcing European and national efforts to understand and develop them better (1). They can increase the provision of labour-market-relevant vocational education and training (VET), supporting national, regional and sectoral upskilling and reskilling strategies, offering learners targeted training for better employment prospects, and helping employers

improve employee retention and productivity. They support the modularisation of qualifications and the validation of prior learning, enabling the inclusion of the most vulnerable and lifelong learning at all levels. However, significant policy progress and research is needed to ensure that microcredentials offer end-users real value. Cedefop has investigated the evolving purposes, roles and effects of microcredentials in relation to European qualifications systems, the preconditions for users to have trust in them, and the support users need to engage with and benefit from them (2).

(1) Cedefop research on microcredentials. See also Cedefop's 2022 briefing note *Are microcredentials becoming a big deal?*

(2) See Cedefop's first, second and third report on this most recent strand of work.

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Research paper

Microcredentials for labour market education and training

First look at mapping microcredentials in European labour-market-related education, training and learning: take-up, characteristics and functions

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Research paper

Microcredentials for labour market education and training

Microcredentials and evolving qualifications systems

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Research paper

Microcredentials for labour market education and training

The added value for end users

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Project page

www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/projects/microcredentials-labour-market-education-and-training

Publications

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Podcasts

Cedefop/ILO podcast on [Microcredentials: powerful new learning tool or just “pouring old wine into new bottles”?](#) Credentials unscripted podcast for the US context.

Available in [Spotify](#) and [Apple Podcasts](#)

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